

Workshop: RDMO for Editors

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DMP4NFDI

Focus & Services

Support the development and provision of standardised
Data and Software Management Plan (DMP/SMP) services within the NFDI.

Services

Hosting
&
Integration with other services

Template standardisation
&
Support for development

Training
&
Support for outreach

Agenda

Agenda

Day 1 - Basics for Editors

- RDMO roles, elements & hierarchy
- Catalog, Sections & Pages
 - **Hands-On**
- Questions settings & formats
 - **Hands-On**

– Break –

- Attributes
 - **Hands-On**

– Break –

- OptionSets and Options
 - **Hands-On**

Wrap Up & Feedback

Day 2 - NFDI DMP Template Framework

- Welcome & Recap Day 1
- Collections
 - **Hands-On**
- Conditions
 - **Hands-On**

– Break –

- NFDI DMP Template Framework (Part I)
 - **Hands-On**

– Break –

- NFDI DMP Template Framework (Part II)
 - **Hands-On**

Wrap Up & Feedback

Housekeeping

Workshop Flow & Tools

Flow

1. **Introduction / Demo** – We'll walk you through what needs to be done.
2. **Hands-On Practice** – You'll put it into practice using our RDMO Demo Instance while we guide you through the process and answer questions (in breakouts or in plenary).
3. **Repeat**

Tools

DMP4NFDI Demo Instance

- URL:
<https://rdmo-test.dmp4nfdi.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/>
- Please Login to create an account for today's workshop
- All content created during this workshop will be deleted

Google folder with workshop documents

- URL:
<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1q4fsHHuYREJF1HbhsQBq7E3VL9J924Hj>

RDMO

user vs. editor

RDMO

From a user's perspective....

In a DFG-funded chemistry project, the PI wants to **create a DMP in RDMO** and work collaboratively with other team members.

What you'll see in RDMO

- Creating an RDMO project
- Choosing a catalog
- Adding team members
- Start filling in RDMO Interview

RDMO

From a user's perspective to an editor's perspective

RDMO editors can create DMP/SMP templates (catalogs) either from scratch or by reusing and adapting parts of existing ones.

What you'll see in RDMO

→ Management interface

Management interface

DMP4 nfdi Management Demo Tools Demo Instance Feedback Language

Management

Catalogs Back New

Filter catalogs × All URI prefixes All sites All editors

Show URIs: Catalogs

Catalog: DFG checklist https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/DFG-Checkliste	
Catalog: RDMO https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/rdmo	
Catalog: Brief questionnaire https://rdmo.fh-potsdam.de/terms/questions/fhpshort	
Catalog: Horizon Europe https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/horizon-europe	
Catalog: Software Management Plan for Researchers https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/smp	
Catalog: SNF https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/snf	
Catalog: DCC Checklist 4.0 https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/dcc	
Catalog: NFDI DMP Template https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/questions/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0	
Catalog: NFDI4Chem_Template https://rdmo.nfdi4chem.de/terms/questions/NFDI4Chem_Vorlage	

Navigation

- Catalogs
- Sections
- Pages
- Question sets
- Questions
- Attributes
- Option sets
- Options
- Conditions
- Tasks
- Views

Export

Export all visible elements.

- XML
- XML (full)
- PDF
- Rich Text Format
- Open Office
- Microsoft Office
- HTML
- Markdown
- mediawiki
- LaTeX

Import

Import an RDMO XML file.

Select file

RDMO

elements & hierarchy

RDMO elements & hierarchy

RDMO elements & hierarchy

Management

Catalog: DFG checklist
<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/DFG-Checkliste>

Filter catalogs x All URI prefixes

Toggle elements: Sections Pages Question sets

Show URIs: Catalogs Sections Pages Question sets Questions Attributes Conditions Option sets

Section: Data description
https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/DFG-Checkliste/data_description

Page: Contentwise data description
https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/DFG-Checkliste/data_description/data_content
<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/id>

Question: How does your project generate new data?
https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/DFG-Checkliste/data_description/data_content/ds_newData 1
https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/creation_methods
https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_new_data

Question: Are existing data reused?
https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/DFG-Checkliste/data_description/data_content/ds_reuse 2
<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/origin>
https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/options/dfg_reuse

Navigation

- Catalogs
- Sections
- Pages
- Question sets
- Questions
- Attributes
- Option sets
- Options
- Conditions
- Tasks
- Views

Export

- Export all visible elements
- XML
- XML (full)
- PDF
- Rich Text Format
- Open Office
- Microsoft Office
- HTML
- Markdown
- mediawiki
- LaTeX

Import

- Import an RDMO XML

Catalog - Section - Page

Creating a Catalog

Overview of the RDMO Hierarchy

Creating a Catalog I

1.

The screenshot shows the DMP4nfdi Management interface. The top navigation bar includes the logo, 'Management' (highlighted with a red box and labeled '1.'), 'Demo Tools', 'Demo Instance', 'Feedback', 'Language', and 'Marisa'. The main content area is titled 'Management' and contains a 'Catalogs' section. In this section, the 'New' button is highlighted with a red box and labeled '2.'. Below the 'New' button are filter controls: 'Filter catalogs', 'All URI prefixes', 'All sites', and 'All editors'. A 'Show URIs' checkbox is checked, and 'Catalogs' is selected. The catalog list includes:

Catalog	URI	Actions
Catalog: DFG checklist	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/DFG-Checkliste	[Menu] [Edit] [Copy] [Add] [Toggle] [Lock] [Download]
Catalog: RDMO	https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/rdmo	[Menu] [Edit] [Copy] [Add] [Toggle] [Lock] [Download]

On the right side, there is a 'Navigation' sidebar with links to Catalogs, Sections, Pages, Question sets, Questions, Attributes, Option sets, Options, Conditions, Tasks, and Views.

Steps

1. Click on **Management** in the top navigation bar.
2. Click on the green **New** button to create your new catalog

Creating a Catalog II

The **URI Prefix** is normally already set by your administrator (e.g. your consortium's name). It indicates where the Catalog was created.

Steps to create a catalog

1. Click on Management in the top navigation bar.
2. Click on the green New button to create your new catalog
3. Fill in the **URI Path**. It should be a unique label for your Catalog, e.g. "dfg-checklist", "rdmo", "horizon-europe".
4. Enter the **Title** of your catalog. The **Help** text should also explain what this catalog is intended for, e.g. "DFG template enriched with [discipline]-specific content". Remember to fill in the fields in all the languages.
5. Click on the **Create and continue editing** button to save your new catalog

Management

Create catalog Back Create and continue editing Create

URI Prefix
https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms
The prefix for the URI of this catalog.

URI Path
The path for the URI of this catalog.

Comment
Additional internal information about this catalog.

Locked Available **Order**
Designates whether this catalog (and its sections, question sets and questions) can be changed. Designates whether this catalog is generally available for projects. The position of this catalog in lists.

Title (English)
The title for this catalog.

Help (English)
The help text for this catalog.

Navigation
Catalogs
Sections
Pages
Question sets
Questions
Attributes
Option sets
Options
Conditions
Tasks
Views

Export
Export all visible elements.
XML
XML (full)
PDF
Rich Text Format
Open Office
Microsoft Office
HTML
Markdown
mediawiki
LaTeX

Import
Import an RDMO XML file.
Select file

Creating a Catalog III

Notice that after saving your catalog, it now has an unique URI with the combination of **URI Prefix** and **URI Path**

Management

Catalog: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test> Back Save and continue editing Save

This catalog is used in **0** projects.

URI Prefix
 ✎
The prefix for the URI of this catalog.

URI Path

The path for the URI of this catalog.

Comment

Additional internal information about this catalog.

Locked Designates whether this catalog (and its sections, question sets and questions) can be changed.

Available Designates whether this catalog is generally available for projects.

Order
 ▾
The position of this catalog in lists.

English German

Title (English)

The title for this catalog.

Help (English)

The help text for this catalog.

Sections
Add existing section Create new section **1.**
The sections of this catalog.

Sites

Navigation

- Catalogs
- Sections
- Pages
- Question sets
- Questions
- Attributes
- Option sets
- Options
- Conditions
- Tasks
- Views

Export

Export all visible elements.

- XML
- XML (full)
- PDF
- Rich Text Format
- Open Office
- Microsoft Office
- HTML
- Markdown
- mediawiki
- LaTeX

Import

Import an RDMO XML file.

Select file

Next element: Section

1. Under the heading “Sections” click on **Create new section** to add the first section to your catalog

Creating a Section

Creating a Section II

You should now see **Create Section** under Management instead of Catalog

Steps to create a section

1. Under the heading "Sections" click on Create new section to add the first section to your catalog.
2. Change the **URI Path** according to the content of the section. Each RDMO element must be unique. Otherwise, RDMO will complain when you try to save.

Management

Create section Back Create and continue editing Create

This section will be added to the catalog <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test>.

URI Prefix

The prefix for the URI of this section.

URI Path

The path for the URI of this section.

Comment

Additional internal information about this section.

Locked
Designates whether this section (and its question sets and questions) can be changed.

Title (English)

Navigation
Catalogs
Sections
Pages
Question sets
Questions
Attributes
Option sets
Options
Conditions
Tasks
Views

Export
Export all visible elements.
XML
XML (full)
PDF
Rich Text Format
Open Office

Management

Create section Back Create and continue editing Create

This section will be added to the catalog <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test>.

URI Prefix

The prefix for the URI of this section.

URI Path

The path for the URI of this section.
Catalog with the uri "https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test" already exists.

Creating a Section III

You should now see **Create Section** under Management instead of Catalog

Steps to create a section

1. Under the heading "Sections" click on Create new section to add the first section to your catalog.
2. Change the **URI Path** according to the content of the section. Each RDMO element must be unique.
3. Enter the **Title** and, if applicable, **Short title** of the Section.
4. Click on the **Create and continue editing** button to save your new section.

Management

Create section Back **Create and continue editing** Create

This section will be added to the catalog <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test>.

URI Prefix
 ✎
The prefix for the URI of this section.

URI Path

The path for the URI of this section.

Comment

Additional internal information about this section.

Locked
Designates whether this section (and its question sets and questions) can be changed.

English German

Title (English)

The title for this section.

Short title (English)

The short title for this section. used in the navigation.

Pages
Add existing page Create new page
The pages of this section.

Editors
 x | v
The sites that can edit this section (in a multi site setup).

Back Create and continue editing Create

Navigation

- Catalogs
- Sections
- Pages
- Question sets
- Questions
- Attributes
- Option sets
- Options
- Conditions
- Tasks
- Views

Export

Export all visible elements.

- XML
- XML (full)
- PDF
- Rich Text Format
- Open Office
- Microsoft Office
- HTML
- Markdown
- mediawiki
- LaTeX

Import

Import an RDMO XML file.

Creating a Section IV

You should now see the URL of your new section and that it is being used in one catalog (the one you just created)

Management

Section: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1> Back Save and continue editing Save

This section is used in **one catalog** ▼

URI Prefix **URI Path**

The prefix for the URI of this section. The path for the URI of this section.

Comment

Additional internal information about this section.

Locked

Designates whether this section (and its question sets and questions) can be changed.

English German

Title (English)

The title for this section.

Short title (English)

The short title for this section. used in the navigation.

Pages

Add existing page Create new page

The pages of this section.

Next element: Page

1. Under the heading "Pages" click on [Create new page](#) to add the first page to your catalog.

1.

Creating a Page

Creating a Page II

You should now see **Create Page** under Management instead of Section

Steps to create a page

1. Under the heading "Pages" click on Create new page to add the first page to your catalog.
2. Change the **URI Path** according to the content of the page.
3. Enter the **Title**, **Short title**, and **Help text** for this page.
4. This time, click on the green **Create** button to save your new page. You will be redirected to your catalog's section

Management

Create page Back Create and continue editing Create

This page will be added to the section <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1>.

URI Prefix
 ✎
The prefix for the URI of this page.

URI Path

The path for the URI of this page.

Comment

Additional internal information about this page.

Locked is collection
Designates whether this page (and its questionsets and questions) can be changed. Designates whether this page is a collection.

English German

Title (English)

The title for this page.

Short title (English)

The short title for this page. used in the navigation.

Help (English)

The help text for this page.

Navigation

- Catalogs
- Sections
- Pages
- Question sets
- Questions
- Attributes
- Option sets
- Options
- Conditions
- Tasks
- Views

Export

Export all visible elements.

- XML
- XML (full)
- PDF
- Rich Text Format
- Open Office
- Microsoft Office
- HTML
- Markdown
- mediawiki
- LaTeX

Import

Import an RDMO XML file.

Section with pages

Your catalog's section now shows the created page. But there is a better way to view all elements of a catalog

Management

Section: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1> [Back](#) [Save and continue editing](#) [Save](#)

This section is used in **one catalog**.▼

URI Prefix
 [✎](#)
The prefix for the URI of this section.

URI Path

The path for the URI of this section.

Comment

Additional internal information about this section.

Locked
Designates whether this section (and its question sets and questions) can be changed.

English German

Title (English)

The title for this section.

Short title (English)

The short title for this section. used in the navigation.

Pages
 | ▼ [✎](#) [✕](#) [+](#)
[Add existing page](#) [Create new page](#)
The pages of this section.

Editors
 [✕](#) | ▼
The sites that can edit this section (in a multi site setup).

[Delete](#) [Back](#) [Save and continue editing](#) [Save](#)

Navigation

- Catalogs
- Sections
- Pages
- Question sets
- Questions
- Attributes
- Option sets
- Options
- Conditions
- Tasks
- Views

Export

Export all visible elements.

- XML
- XML (full)
- PDF
- Rich Text Format
- Open Office
- Microsoft Office
- HTML
- Markdown
- mediawiki
- LaTeX

Import

Import an RDMO XML file.

[→](#)

Nested view of catalog elements

Steps to open a nested view

1. Click on **Management** in the top navigation bar. You will see all available catalogs.
2. Find your new created catalog. You can use the filter text field.
3. Click on the first icon to the right to open the nested view of your catalog.

1.

Management Demo Tools Demo Instance Feedback Language

Management

Catalogs Back New

2. Filter catalogs x All URI prefixes All sites All editors

Show URIs: Catalogs

Catalog: DFG checklist https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/DFG-Checkliste	
Catalog: RDMO https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/rdmo	
Catalog: Brief questionnaire https://rdmo.fh-potsdam.de/terms/questions/fhpshort	
Catalog: Horizon Europe https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/horizon-europe	

Navigation

- Catalogs
- Sections
- Pages
- Question sets
- Questions
- Attributes
- Option sets
- Options
- Conditions
- Tasks
- Views

Export

Export all visible elements.

- XML
- XML (full)

Catalog: Marisa's test catalog for workshop

<https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test>

3.

Nested view of catalog elements

The screenshot displays the RDMO Management interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the RDMO logo, 'Management', 'Demo Tools', 'Demo Instance', 'Feedback', and 'Language'. The main content area is titled 'Management' and shows a hierarchical view of catalog elements:

- Catalog:** Marisa's test catalog for workshop
URL: `https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test`
- Section:** My first section
URL: `https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1`
- Page:** My first page
URL: `https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1`

Below the catalog information, there is a filter input field labeled 'Filter catalogs' and a dropdown menu for 'All URI prefixes'. A 'Toggle elements' section allows switching between 'Sections', 'Pages', and 'Question sets'. A 'Show URIs' section has checkboxes for 'Catalogs', 'Sections', 'Pages', 'Question sets', 'Questions', 'Attributes', 'Conditions', and 'Option sets', all of which are checked.

On the right side, there is a 'Navigation' sidebar with a list of elements: Catalogs, Sections, Pages, Question sets, Questions, Attributes, Option sets, Options, Conditions, Tasks, and Views. Below this is an 'Export' section with the text 'Export all visible elements.' and a list of export formats: XML, XML (full), PDF, Rich Text Format, Open Office, Microsoft Office, HTML, Markdown, mediawiki, and LaTeX. At the bottom right, there is an 'Import' section with the text 'Import an RDMO XML file.' and a 'Select file' button with a right-pointing arrow.

Hands-on:
Catalog - Section- Page

RDMO

Exercise 1: Catalog - Section - Page

10 min

Indicate with a zoom reaction when you're finished

Raise your hand or write in the chat if you have questions

Create a Catalog containing a Section and a Page

1. Click on **Management** in the top navigation bar and create a new catalog
2. Give your catalog a unique **URI Path** and **Title**
(Please **add your name to the URI Path** and/or title to avoid duplicates)
3. Complete the structure of the Catalog adding a “*Data description*” **Section** and a “*Content Data Description*” **Page**
4. Open the nested view of your catalog

Catalog - Section - Page User vs. Editor

Catalog

POV: User vs. Editor

The screenshot shows the 'RDMO Workshop for Editors' page. The top navigation bar includes 'DMP4 nfdi', 'Management', 'Demo Tools', 'Demo Instance', 'Feedback', and 'Language'. The main content area is divided into several sections: 'Description' (No description available), 'Catalog' (Horizon Europe), 'Tasks' (No tasks are configured for this project), 'Views' (No views are configured for this project), 'Members' (A table with one member: Marisabel Gonzalez Ocanto, ocanto@zbmed.de, Owner), and 'Snapshots' (No snapshots found). A right sidebar contains 'Options', 'Answer questions', 'View answers', 'Export', and 'Import values'. The 'Catalog' section is highlighted with a blue box, and the description text is highlighted with a green box.

Description No description available.

Catalog **Horizon Europe**

This catalog is intended for research projects funded by EU Horizon Europe. It is compiled according to the Data Management Plan Template, Version 1.0 from May 5, 2021. Some of the EU questions are broken down into sub-questions. In addition, for many questions there is the option of answering the question on a dataset-specific basis. There is a suitable view for the output of the data management plan, which

- outputs the data management plan in the deliverable form desired by the EU;
- uses the original EU questions;
- automatically inserts references to questions that have already been asked in a similar form.

Options

Answer questions

View answers

Update project information
Update project catalog
Update parent project
Update project tasks
Update project views
Copy project
Delete project

Add member
Create snapshot

Back to projects overview

Export

RDMO XML
CSV (comma separated)
CSV (semicolon separated)
JSON

Import values

Import from file

Select file

Members

User	E-Mail	Role
Marisabel Gonzalez Ocanto	ocanto@zbmed.de	Owner

Snapshots

No snapshots found.

User's interface (after creating a project and selecting a catalog)

The screenshot shows the 'Management' page for the 'Horizon Europe' catalog. The top navigation bar is the same as the user interface. The main content area includes: 'Catalog' (https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/horizon-europe), 'URI Prefix' (https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms), 'URI Path' (horizon-europe), 'Comment' (RDMO questionnaire for the funding framework program "Horizon Europe" (2021-2027) of the European Commission), 'Additional internal information about this catalog.', 'Locked' (unchecked), 'Available' (checked), 'Order' (5), 'Title (English)' (Horizon Europe), and 'Help (English)' (This catalog is intended for research projects funded by EU Horizon Europe. It is compiled according to the Data Management Plan Template, Version 1.0 from May 5, 2021. Some of the EU questions are broken down into sub-questions. In addition, for many questions there is the option of...). A right sidebar contains 'Navigation' (Catalogs, Sections, Pages, Question sets, Attributes, Option sets, Options, Conditions, Tasks, Views), 'Export' (Export all views, XML, XML (full), PDF, Rich Text Fo, Open Office, Microsoft O, HTML, Markdown, mediawiki, LaTeX), and 'Import' (Import an R, Select file). The 'Title (English)' and 'Help (English)' sections are highlighted with blue and green boxes respectively.

Management

Catalog: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/horizon-europe> Back Save and continue editing Save

This catalog is used in **one project**.

URI Prefix The prefix for the URI of this catalog.

URI Path The path for the URI of this catalog.

Comment

RDMO questionnaire for the funding framework program "Horizon Europe" (2021-2027) of the European Commission

Additional internal information about this catalog.

Locked Available Designates whether this catalog (and its sections, question sets and questions) can be changed. Designates whether this catalog is generally available for projects.

Order The position of this catalog in lists.

English German

Title (English)

The title for this catalog.

Help (English)

This catalog is intended for research projects funded by EU Horizon Europe. It is compiled according to the Data Management Plan Template, Version 1.0 from May 5, 2021. Some of the EU questions are broken down into sub-questions. In addition, for many questions there is the option of

The help text for this catalog.

Section

POV: User vs. Editor

The screenshot shows the user's interface for editing a section. The top navigation bar includes 'DMP4 nfdi', 'Back to project', 'Management', 'Demo Tools', 'Demo Instance', 'Feedback', and 'Language'. The breadcrumb trail is 'My Projects / RDMO Workshop for Editors / General', with 'General' highlighted in a blue box. The main content area is titled 'Basic information on the project' and contains several form fields: 'Project reference number', 'Project acronym', 'Project title', 'Date', and 'DMP version'. A right-hand sidebar titled 'Overview' lists project details and navigation options. Below it, a 'Progress' bar shows '0 of 22' items, and a 'Navigation' menu lists various categories, with 'General' highlighted in a blue box. At the bottom, there are 'Back' and 'Proceed' buttons.

User's interface (answering / navigating catalog)

The screenshot shows the editor's interface for editing a section. The top navigation bar includes 'DMP4 nfdi', 'Management', 'Demo Tools', and 'Demo Instance'. The main content area is titled 'Management' and shows the section URL: 'https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/horizon-europe/general', with 'Back' and 'Save and' buttons. The interface is divided into several sections: 'URI Prefix' (https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms) and 'URI Path' (horizon-europe/general), both with edit icons; a 'Comment' text area; 'Additional internal information about this section' with a 'Locked' checkbox; and language selection options for 'English' and 'German'. Below these are two more form fields: 'Title (English)' with the value 'General' (highlighted in a blue box) and 'Short title (English)'. The 'Title (English)' field has a description: 'The title for this section.' The 'Short title (English)' field has a description: 'The short title for this section. used in the navigation.'

Page

POV: User vs. Editor

DMP4 nfdi Back to project Management Demo Tools Demo Instance Feedback Language

My Projects / RDMO Workshop for Editors / General

Basic information on the project

This questionnaire is intended for research projects funded by EU Horizon Europe. It is compiled according to the Data Management Plan Template, Version 1.0 from May 5, 2021. Some of the EU questions are broken down into sub-questions. In addition, for many questions there is the option of answering the question on a dataset-specific basis. There is a suitable view for the output of the data management plan, which

- outputs the data management plan in the deliverable form desired by the EU,
- uses the original EU questions,
- automatically inserts references to questions that have already been asked in a similar form

Project reference number:
With which grant number was the funding awarded?

Project acronym:
Short title / acronym of the project

Project title:
Full title of the project

Date:
Today's date

DMP version:
Which version of the data management plan is this?

0 of 22

Back Proceed

Overview

Project: RDMO Workshop for Editors
Catalog: Horizon Europe

Show management panels

Reload page
Back to my projects

Progress

Navigation

Grey entries will be conditionally skipped based on your input.

General

- Basic information on the project
- Disciplinary and and technical classifica...
- FAIR data
- Other research outputs
- Allocation of resources
- Data security
- Ethics
- Other aspects

Back Proceed

User's interface (answering / navigating catalog)

DMP4 nfdi Management Demo Tools Demo Instance Feedback Language

Management

Page: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/questions/horizon-europe/general/general> Back Save and continue editing Save

This page is used in **one section**.

URI Prefix
 The prefix for the URI of this page.

URI Path
 The path for the URI of this page.

Comment

Additional internal information about this page.

Locked
Designates whether this page (and its questionsets and questions) can be changed.

is collection
Designates whether this page is a collection.

English German

Title (English)
 The title for this page.

Short title (English)

The short title for this page. used in the navigation.

Help (English)
This questionnaire is intended for research projects funded by EU Horizon Europe. It is compiled according to the Data Management Plan Template, Version 1.0 from May 5, 2021 . Some of the EU questions are broken down into sub-questions. In addition, for many questions there is the option of

The help text for this page.

Questions

Settings and formats

Creating Questions Sets & Questions

Overview of the RDMO Hierarchy

- **Catalog:** top-level container of your DMP template
 - **Section:** Major divisions within the Catalog containing pages
 - **Page:** subdivisions of a section containing questions or question sets
 - **Question sets:** group of related questions within a page, e.g. responsible(s) for handling data. May contain other question sets or individual questions.
 - **Questions**
 - **Questions:** has a text, which will be shown in bold to the user and can accept different response formats (Widgets).
 - **Option sets:**
 - **Options:**

Creating Questions I

Steps to create a Question

1. Open the nested view of your catalog
2. On the **Page element**, click on the Plus (+) icon and select **Add Question**

Catalog: Marisa's test catalog for workshop
<https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test>

Management

Catalog: Marisa's test catalog for workshop
<https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test>

Filter catalogs × All URI prefixes

Toggle elements: Sections Pages Question sets

Show URIs: Catalogs Sections Pages Question sets Questions Attributes Conditions Option sets

Section: My first section
<https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1> 1

Page: My first page
<https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1> 1

1.

2.

Add question
Add question set

Navigation: Catalogs Sections Pages Questions Question sets Attributes Option sets Options Conditions Tasks Views

Export:

Creating Questions II

Steps to create a Question

1. Open the nested view of your catalog
2. On the **Page element**, click on the Plus (+) icon and select Add Question
3. Change the **URI Path** according to the content of the question (not shown here)
4. Enter the **Text** of your question and a **Help** text if needed. Remember to do it in all languages
5. Select an **Attribute** (We will deep dive later into them)
6. Select a **Widget Type** and **Value Type**
7. Click on the green **Create** button to save your new question (not shown here)

4.

English German

Text (English)

The text for this question.

Help (English)

5.

The help text for this question.

Name (English)

The name displayed for this question.

Attribute

6.

Create new attribute

The attribute this question belongs to.

Widget type	Value type	Unit	Width
<input type="text" value="Text"/>	<input type="text" value="Text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Type of widget for this question.	Type of value for this question.	Unit for this question.	Width for the widget of this question (optional, full width: 12).

Creating Questions III

Widget Types

Selecting a widget type

- **Text** an unwrapped line
- **Textarea** a variable number of wrapped lines
- **Yes/No** a simple binary input
- **Range slider** to select an ordinal level from a given range
- **Date picker** to select a date from a calendar
- **File upload** field for entering a file name or a window to facilitate the selection of a file stored on the computer.

Checkboxes, Radio buttons, and Drop-down will be covered later

Creating Questions IV

Widget Types from a user's perspective

Text area

If created, are already existing, similar research data available and why is their subsequent use not possible or useful here?

[Back](#) [Proceed](#)

File

File?

Current file: attributes.xml

Drag 'n drop some files here, or click to select files.

Date picker

Date:

Today's date

November 2025

Mo	Tu	We	Th	Fr	Sa	Su
27	28	29	30	31	1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30

management plan is this?

Yes/No

Will persistent identifiers (PIDs) be used for this data set?

The purpose of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) is to ensure the permanent reference of (in particular) digital objects like online publications and research data. When traditional hyperlinks are used as reference, they point directly to the storage location of the data. The problem is, that if the storage location is changed, the link will not work anymore. A PID serves as an intermediate from which requests are directed to the current object location (this is called "resolving" of a PID). The PID stays the same, even if the storage location changes. While a mere hyperlink in this case would lead to nowhere, via the PID the object is still accessible. A widespread PID system is the DOI system (Digital Object Identifier), which is based on the Handle system.

Yes No

Range Slider

What are the personnel costs associated with the data documentation and the creation of metadata in the project?

Please estimate the effort in person months.

4 PM

Creating Questions V

POV: User vs. Manager

Basic information on the project

This questionnaire is intended for research projects funded by EU Horizon Plan Template, Version 1.0 from May 5, 2021. Some of the EU questionnaire questions there is the option of answering the question on a dataset-s management plan, which

- outputs the data management plan in the deliverable form design
- uses the original EU questions,
- automatically inserts references to questions that have already

Project reference number:

With which grant number was the funding awarded?

English German

Text (English)

Project reference number:

The text for this question.

Help (English)

With which grant number was the funding awarded?

The help text for this question.

Name (English)

The name displayed for this question.

Attribute

https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/funder/grant_nr

Create new attribute

The attribute this question belongs to.

Widget type	Value type	Unit	Width
Text	Text		

Type of widget for this question.

Type of value for this question.

Unit for this question.

Width for the widget of this question (optional, full)

Creating Question Sets I

Steps to create a Question Set

1. Open the nested view of your catalog
2. On the **Page element**, click on the Plus (+) icon and select **Add question set**

Catalog: Marisa's test catalog for workshop
<https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test>

Management

Catalog: Marisa's test catalog for workshop
<https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test>

Filter catalogs × All URI prefixes

Toggle elements: Sections Pages Question sets

Show URIs: Catalogs Sections Pages Question sets Questions Attributes Conditions Option sets

Section: My first section
<https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1> 1

Page: My first page
<https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1> 1

1.

2.

- Add question
- Add question set

Navigation: Catalogs Sections Pages Question sets Questions Attributes Option sets Options Conditions Tasks Views

Export:

Creating Question Sets II

Steps to create a Question Set

1. Open the nested view of your catalog
2. On the **Page** element, click on the Plus (+) icon and select **Add question set**
3. Change the **URI Path** according to the content of the question set
4. Enter the **Title** of your question set and a **Help** text if needed. Remember to do it in all languages
5. Click on the green **Create** button to save your new question set

Create question set

[Back](#) [Create and continue editing](#) [Create](#)

URI Prefix

The prefix for the URI of this question set.

URI Path **3.**

The path for the URI of this question set.

Comment

Additional internal information about this question set.

Locked **is collection**
Designates whether this question set (and its questions) can be changed. Designates whether this question set is a collection.

4.

English German

Title (English)

The title for this question set.

Help (English)

The help text for this question set.

Creating Question Sets III

Steps to add Questions to a Question Set

1. Open the nested view of your catalog
2. On the Question Set element, click on the Plus (+) icon and select [Add question](#)
3. Follow the previous steps to create questions

The screenshot displays the RDMO interface for a catalog named "Marisa's test for workshop". The breadcrumb path is `https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test`. The interface shows a hierarchical structure with the following elements:

- Catalog:** Marisa's test for workshop (URI: `https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test`)
- Section:** My first section (URI: `https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1`)
- Page:** My first page (URI: `https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1`)
- Question set:** Project duration (URI: `https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1/question-set-1`)

At the bottom of the "Question set" element, a red circle highlights the Plus (+) icon. A tooltip menu is open, showing two options: "Add question" (underlined) and "Add question set".

On the right side, a navigation sidebar is visible with the following items: Navig, Catalogs, Sections, Pages, Question, Question, Attribute, Option s, Options, Conditio, Tasks, Views, Expo, Export a, XML, XML (ful).

Nested view of catalog elements

The screenshot displays the 'Management' interface of the DMP4nfdi system. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the logo, 'Management', 'Demo Tools', 'Demo Instance', and 'Feedback' links. The main content area is titled 'Management' and shows a hierarchical view of a catalog.

Catalog: Marisa's test for workshop
URL: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test>

Filter catalogs: [x] All URI prefixes: [v]

Toggle elements: Sections Pages Question sets

Show URIs: Catalogs Sections Pages Question sets Questions Attributes Conditions Option sets

Section: My first section
URL: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1> 1

Page: My first page
URL: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1> 1

Question set: Project duration
URL: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1/question-set-1> 1

Question: When does the project start?
URL: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1/question-set-1/question-1> 1
External URL: https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/schedule/project_start

Question: When does the project end?
URL: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1/question-set-1/question-2> 2
External URL: https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/schedule/project_end

Question: Who is funding the project
URL: <https://rdmo.dmp4nfdi.de/terms/questions/marisa-test/section-1/page-1/question-1> 1
External URL: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/funder/name>

Hands-on: Question Sets - Question

RDMO

Exercise 2 - Questions & Question Sets

20 min

Indicate with a zoom reaction when you're finished

Raise your hand or write in the chat if you have questions

- I. Open the nested view of your catalog and add the following **Question** to your “Content Data Description” Page choosing a suitable widget for your question

What is the provenance of the data?

The history of origin (provenance) of the data and even, if relevant for research data management, the provenance of the physical objects on which the data is based can be entered in this text area. .

Attribute: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/provenance/content>

- II. Add a **Question Set** to your “Content Data Description” Page with the following information

If the data is re-used

Who created the dataset?

Attribute: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/creator/name>

Under which address, PID or URL can the dataset be found?

Attribute: <https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/uri>

Attributes

Attributes

Attributes in RDMO

RDMO data model

- domain model is the central part of the data model
- Connection between questions from the questionnaire and the answers given by the user
- Every information of a user's project is represented by an attribute
- Every question or question set must have an attribute to be connected to

<https://rdmo.readthedocs.io/en/latest/management/data-model.html>

Attributes

Getting user information - API

RDMO data model

Tree-like structure of the data model

- Attributes are the leaves
- To access the attribute, the whole path should be used

```
/api/v1/projects # project "object properties" / general
/api/v1/projects/projects # project "data properties" / metadata
/api/v1/projects/projects/{id} # project "data properties" / metadata

/api/v1/projects/values # all values from all projects
/api/v1/projects/projects/{parent_lookup_project}/values # all values from one project
/api/v1/projects/projects/{parent_lookup_project}/values/{id} # a chosen value assignment
/api/v1/projects/values/{id} # a chosen value assignment (shorter form)

/api/v1/projects/snapshots # all snapshots from all projects
/api/v1/projects/projects/{parent_lookup_project}/snapshots # all snapshots from one project
/api/v1/projects/projects/{parent_lookup_project}/snapshots/{id} # a chosen snapshot
/api/v1/projects/snapshots/{id} # a chosen snapshot (shorter form)
```

<https://rdmo.readthedocs.io/en/latest/administration/api.html>

```
/api
/v1
/projects
/projects
/{parent_lookup_project}
/values
/{id} ← attribute
```

Attributes

Structure of an attribute

URI prefix

URI path

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms> /[domain](#)/project/dataset/reproducibility

307 official attributes

project

dataset

reproducibility

Problem:

- no standards
- Same attributes for different questions
- Same questions with different attributes

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository page for the file `attributes.xml` in the `rdmorganiser/domain` directory. The file content is as follows:

```
1 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
2 <rdmo xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/" created="2024-09-24T08:29:53.032244+02:00" version="2.0.0">
3   <attribute dc:uri="https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project">
4     <uri_prefix>https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms</uri_prefix>
5     <key>project</key>
6     <path>project</path>
7     <dc:comment/>
8   </attribute>
9 </rdmo>
10 <attribute dc:uri="https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/acronym">
```

Attributes

Structure of an attribute

Problem:

Difficult to find the right attribute

vs.

Easy to create a new attribute

Where can i search for an attribute?

Hands-on: Attributes

Attributes

Exercise 3

add 1-2 new questions to your catalog and try to find the right attribute for the specific question using different tools:

- group 1: [rdmo-terms](#)
- group 2: [table with mapping](#)
- group 3: [rdmo-catalog](#)
- group 4: everything of group 1-3

Group 4

Group 1

The screenshot shows the 'rdmo-terms' website. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'Questions', 'Domain', 'Options', 'Conditions', 'Tasks', and 'Views'. Below the menu, the title 'rdmo-terms' is displayed. A paragraph of text explains that RDMO is a tool for systematic planning and implementation of data management. Below the text, there are six columns, each representing a different category: Questions, Domain, Options, Conditions, Tasks, and Views. Each column contains a list of sub-items and a 'Go to' button. For example, the 'Questions' column lists 'Contains', 'Catalogs', 'Sections', 'Question sets', and 'Questions', with a 'Go to questions' button below. The 'Domain' column lists 'Contains', 'Attributes', and 'Attributes', with a 'Go to domain' button. The 'Options' column lists 'Contains', 'Option sets', and 'Options', with a 'Go to options' button. The 'Conditions' column lists 'Contains', 'Conditions', and 'Conditions', with a 'Go to conditions' button. The 'Tasks' column lists 'Contains', 'Tasks', and 'Tasks', with a 'Go to tasks' button. The 'Views' column lists 'Contains', 'Views', and 'Views', with a 'Go to views' button. At the bottom, there is a note about contacting the team if there are suggestions or problems.

Group 2

The screenshot shows a table with mapping. The table has columns for 'Attribute', 'Question', 'Help', 'Value Type', and 'Options'. The first row shows the question 'Which measures of quality assurance are taken for this dataset?' with the attribute 'https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/rate' and value type 'text'. The second row shows the question 'How much data are produced per year?' with the attribute 'https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/reproducibility' and value type 'integer'. The table also includes a 'Catalog' column with 'DFG checklist' and 'Horizon Europe' entries.

Group 3

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository page for 'rdmorganiser/rdmo-catalog/tree/main/rdmorganiser/questions'. The left sidebar shows a file explorer with the following structure: 'main' (selected), 'attributes.xml', 'options', and 'questions'. The 'questions' directory is expanded, showing files: 'DFG-Checkliste.md', 'SMP_Readme.md', 'questions-DFG-Checkliste.xml', 'questions-dcc.xml', 'questions-fhpsshort.xml', 'questions-horizon-europe.xml', 'questions-rdmo.xml', 'questions-smp.xml', and 'questions-snf.xml'. The main content area shows a list of files with their names and last commit messages. The files listed are: 'DFG-Checkliste.md' (Attributanpassung (#1...)), 'SMP_Readme.md' (rename main branch), 'questions-DFG-Checkliste.xml' (Revised language for...), 'questions-dcc.xml' (Prepare first 2.x-comp...), 'questions-fhpsshort.xml' (Prepare first 2.x-comp...), 'questions-horizon-europe.xml' (Prepare first 2.x-comp...), 'questions-rdmo.xml' (Uag running projects), 'questions-smp.xml' (correct wrong prefixe...), and 'questions-snf.xml' (Prepare first 2.x-comp...).

Attributes

Exercise 3

Group 2

Group 4

Either doubleclick
Or rightclick -> open with -> firefox

Attributes

Exercise 3 - solution

Question 1: *Is there someone you can go to if you have questions about how your data is being handled?*

RDMO: Who is/are the contact person(s) for data management questions?

https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/partner/contact_person/name

DFG Checklist: Who is responsible for adequate handling of the research data (description of the roles and responsibilities within the project)?

<https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/support>

NFDI DMP Template Framework: Who is the main contact person for questions related to data management?

TF: https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/data_management/name

Attributes

Exercise 3 - solution

Question 2: **Can you ensure that the participants are not mentioned by name?**

https://rdmorganiser.github.io/terms/domain/project/dataset/sensitive_data/personal_data/anonymization

RDMO: Will the data be anonymised or pseudonymised?

Option sets

Overview of the RDMO Hierarchy

- **Catalog:** top-level container of your DMP template
 - **Section:** Major divisions within the Catalog containing pages
 - **Page:** subdivisions of a section containing questions or question sets
 - **Question sets:** group of related questions within a page, e.g. responsible(s) for handling data.
 - **Questions**
 - **Questions:** has a text, which will be shown in bold to the user and can accept different response formats (Widgets).
 - **Option sets:** a predefined group of answer choices used for questions
 - **Options:** the components of Option sets

Option sets

User perspective

- Various Widget types

Checkboxes

Instrument calibration (accuracy/scale)

Multiple measurements, observations or samples

Verification by experts

Computer-assisted data collection

Standardized methods and protocols (with clear instructions)

Other:

Radio buttons

Please enter your entries line by line. You can add lines using the green button and remove them using the blue cross (×).

Instrument calibration (accuracy/scale)

Multiple measurements, observations or samples

Verification by experts

Computer-assisted data collection

Standardized methods and protocols (with clear instructions)

Other:

Select drop down

Please enter your entries line by line. You can add lines using the green button and remove them using the blue cross (×).

Select ...

Instrument calibration (accuracy/scale)

Multiple measurements, observations or samples

Verification by experts

Computer-assisted data collection

Standardized methods and protocols (with clear instructions)

Other

Select drop down free

Please enter your entries line by line. You can add lines using the green button and remove them using the blue cross (×).

st

Instrument calibration (accuracy/scale)

Computer-assisted data collection

Standardized methods and protocols (with clear instructions)

Option sets

Option sets and Options

- Static vs. dynamic option sets
 - A) Create and add specific options to an option set
 - B) Select option set provider for dynamic option sets

Option sets

How to assign Option sets to questions

- Assign option sets to questions via the option sets tab
- Allow multiple answers – “is collection” required for checkboxes
- Add multiple option sets to a question

The screenshot displays the configuration interface for a question. At the top, there are four main sections: 'Widget type' (set to 'Checkboxes'), 'Value type' (set to 'Option'), 'Unit' (empty), and 'Width' (empty). Below these are tabs for 'Conditions', 'Option sets', 'Range', 'Default', and 'Editors'. The 'Option sets' tab is highlighted with a red border and contains two buttons: 'Add existing optionset' and 'Create new optionset'. A red arrow points from the 'Option' value type dropdown to the 'Option sets' tab.

Widget type
Checkboxes x | v
Type of widget for this question.

Value type
Option x | v
Type of value for this question.

Unit
Unit for this question.

Width
Width for the widget of this question (optional, full width: 12).

Conditions **Option sets** Range Default Editors

Option sets
Add existing optionset Create new optionset
Option sets for this question.

Option sets

Create a new option set

- Option sets and Options in management interface

The screenshot displays the 'Management' interface for option sets. At the top, there is a 'Back' button and a green 'New' button, which is highlighted by a red arrow. Below this is a search bar labeled 'Filter option sets' and a dropdown menu showing the URL 'https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/t/'. To the right of the search bar is a dropdown menu labeled 'All editors'. The main content area lists ten option sets, each with a URL and a set of icons (list, edit, add, lock, delete). The 'Option sets' link in the navigation sidebar on the right is highlighted with a red box.

Option set	URL	Actions
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/contributor_responsibilities	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/dataset_availability	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/dataset_quality	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/file_formats	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/host/versioning_tool	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/personal_data	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/pid_system	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/resources_non-personnel	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/reused_Datasets_URL	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️
Option set:	https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/security_measures	☰ ✎ + 🔒 🗑️

Navigation

- Catalogs
- Sections
- Pages
- Question sets
- Questions
- Attributes
- Option sets**
- Options
- Conditions
- Tasks
- Views

Export

Export all visible elements.

- XML
- XML (full)
- PDF
- Rich Text Format
- Open Office
- Microsoft Office
- HTML
- Markdown
- mediawiki
- LaTeX

Option sets

Create a new option set

- URI path
- Add options or provider
- Order
- (Conditions for option sets)

Management

Create option set Back Create and continue editing Create

URI Prefix

The prefix for the URI of this option set.

URI Path

The path for the URI of this option set.

Comment

Additional internal information about this option set.

Locked
Designates whether this option set (and its options) can be changed.

Options
Add existing option Create new option
The list of options for this option set.

Conditions
Add existing condition Create new condition
The list of conditions evaluated for this option set.

Provider

The provider for this optionset. If set, it will create dynamic options for this optionset.

Editors

The sites that can edit this option set (in a multi site setup).

Back Create and continue editing Create

Option sets

Create a new option

- Open Option set in nested view
- Add new options via **+**-Button or copy existing options

Management

Option sets Back New

Filter option sets ✕ https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/contributor_responsibilitie All editors

Option set: https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/contributor_responsibilitie ☰ + - 📄

Option set: https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/dataset_availability ☰ + - 📄

Option set: https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/dataset_quality ☰ + - 📄

Navigation

- Catalogs
- Sections
- Pages
- Question sets
- Questions
- Attributes
- Option sets
- Options
- Conditions

Management

Option set: https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/dmp4nfdi/v1-0-0/file_formats ☰ + - 📄 Back

Filter option sets ✕ All URI prefixes

Show URIs: Options

Option: Application ☰ + - 📄
<https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/ff00>

Option: Audio ☰ + - 📄
<https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/ff01>

Option: Image ☰ + - 📄
<https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/ff02>

Option: Message ☰ + - 📄
<https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/ff03>

Option: Model ☰ + - 📄
<https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/ff04>

Option: Text ☰ + - 📄
<https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/ff05>

Option: Video ☰ + - 📄
<https://dmp.service.base4nfdi.de/terms/options/ff06>

Option sets

Create a new option

- URI Path for Options
- Option Text
- Help vs View text
- Additional Input
 - A) None
 - B) Text
 - C) Text area

Management

Create option Back Create and continue editing Create

URI Prefix ✎

The prefix for the URI of this option.

URI Path

The path for the URI of this option.

Comment

Additional internal information about this option.

Locked
Designates whether this option can be changed.

English **German**

Text (English)

The text for this option.

Help (English)

The help text for this option.

View text (English)

The view text for this option.

Additional input

----- Text Textarea

Designates whether an additional input is possible for this option.

Editors

✕ ⌵

The sites that can edit this option (in a multi site setup).

Back Create and continue editing Create

Hands-on: Option sets

Option sets

Exercise 4 – Create an option set

- Create a new checkbox option set
- Assign the option set to a question in your catalog

Which tools, software, technologies or processes are used to generate or collect new data?

This information is necessary to be able to reconstruct the process by which the data was generated. It is also a prerequisite to judge the objectivity, reliability and validity of the data set.

For reproducible data it is also required to re-generate the data if necessary. Therefore all devices, software, software version and also information about the procedure necessary to be able to re-create the data must be preserved.

- Observations (by humans, instruments or sensors)
- Polls
- Surveys
- Laboratory experiments
- Social science experiments
- Field experiments
- Analysis, derivation or compilation from other data sources
- Calculations
- Bibliographies
- Catalogues, repositories or databases
- Crowdsourcing
- Web scraping
- Models
- Simulations
- Other:

Option sets

Summary

- Option sets can be used with different kinds of widget types in the interview
- You can create static or dynamic option sets
- Option sets are assigned to a question in the question settings

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Wrap-up & Feedback

Overview of the RDMO Hierarchy

- **Catalog:** top-level container of your DMP template
 - **Section:** Major divisions within the Catalog containing pages
 - **Page:** subdivisions of a section containing questions or question sets
 - **Question sets:** group of related questions within a page, e.g. responsible(s) for handling data.
 - **Questions**
 - **Questions:** has a text, which will be shown in bold to the user and can accept different response formats (Widgets).
 - **Option sets:** a predefined group of answer choices used for questions
 - **Options:** the components of Option sets

Agenda

Day 1 - Basics for Editors

- RDMO roles, elements & hierarchy
 - Catalog, Sections & Pages
 - **Hands-On**
 - Questions settings & formats
 - **Hands-On**
 - Break –
 - Attributes
 - **Hands-On**
 - Break –
 - OptionSets and Options
 - **Hands-On**
- Wrap Up & Feedback

Day 2 - NFDI DMP Template Framework

- Welcome & Recap Day 1
 - Collections
 - **Hands-On**
 - Conditions
 - **Hands-On**
 - Break –
 - NFDI DMP Template Framework (Part I)
 - **Hands-On**
 - Break –
 - NFDI DMP Template Framework (Part II)
 - **Hands-On**
- Wrap Up & Feedback

Feedback

From a user's perspective to an editor's perspective

How was working with RDMO?

What did you like about today?

What can be improved?

